

Tabla de artículos primarios identificados en la RSL.

Id	Artículos Primarios	Año	Ref.
A1	Process Debt: a First Exploration	2020	[1]
A2	Process Debt: Definition, Risks and Management.	2024	[2]
A3	The Pandora's box of social, process, and people debts in software engineering.	2022	[3]
A4	Technical-, social-and process debt in large-scale agile: an exploratory case-study	2019	[4]
A5	A Multivocal Literature Review on Non-Technical Debt in Software Development: An Insight into Process, Social, People, Organizational, and Culture Debt	2024	[24]
A6	A study of factors that lead development teams to incur technical debt in software projects	2018	[15]
A7	A systematic mapping study on technical debt definition	2015	[25]
A8	A systems perspective on technical debt	2021	[26]
A9	A taxonomy of assets for the development of software-intensive products and services	2023	[27]
A10	Actions and impediments for technical debt prevention: results from a global family of industrial surveys	2020	[14]
A11	Technical debt: towards a crisper definition report on the 4th international workshop on managing technical debt	2013	[22]
A12	Beyond Technical Debt Unravelling Organisational Debt Concept	2024	[28]
A13	Exploring Process Debt in Large-Scale Agile Software Development For Secure Telecom Solutions	2024	[16]
A14	Identification and management of technical debt: A systematic mapping study	2016	[29]
A15	Multivocal Literature Review on Non-Technical Debt in Software Development: An Exploratory Study.	2023	[17]
A16	Society 5.0 and Soft Skills in Agile Global Software Development	2022	[18]
A17	Technical debt is not only about code and we need to be aware about it	2021	[19]
A18	Technical Debt Management: Definition of a Technical Debt Reduction Software Engineering Methodology for SMEs	2019	[20]
A19	Towards a taxonomy of code review smells	2022	[21]
A20	Towards an ontology of terms on technical debt	2014	[23]

Acrónimos utilizados: Ref.: referencia.